

Arctic Frontier Fortress: The Case for Militarizing Svalbard

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ABSTRACT

Svalbard is a sparsely populated collection of islands to the north of Norway and northwest of major naval and air bases in Russia. Given its geographic position and complex international status, regulated by a 1920 treaty, Svalbard has long been a target for Russian and Soviet aggression, and recent developments in the Arctic and in Europe suggest that the threat from Moscow remains relevant today. By examining Svalbard's geographic position, its history, the presence of Russian assets on the islands, and current Russian stances towards the Arctic, it becomes clear that Svalbard holds considerable strategic significance to Moscow. NATO and the United States must reevaluate their stance towards Svalbard and consider taking steps to militarize the islands and turn them into a fortress against Russian encroachment in the north.

KEYWORDS: Svalbard, Russia, Arctic, Norway, Disinformation, Arktikugol', Franz Josef Land

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Scattered among the daily flow of news from Ukraine's frontlines and China's harassment of fishing vessels in the South China Sea are stories about Svalbard. This archipelago of large and mostly frozen islands sits roughly 600 miles north of Scandinavia and is the sovereign territory of Norway. However, due to their ambiguous international status and history, these islands have been identified as a

potential site for conflict between NATO and Russia. There is indeed reason to pay attention to these islands and Russia's activities in the Arctic. However, Svalbard is far from NATO's Achilles heel and should not be treated as such. Rather, the archipelago represents an opportunity greater for NATO than for Russia.

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This report will thus seek to establish Svalbard's history, its geopolitical and geographical significance, present-day activities there by relevant actors, and how NATO can turn these remote islands into a vital asset in its competition with Russia. The research below was conducted entirely through open-source means. Secondary source research included examining media reporting and peer-reviewed scholarly journal articles, while primary sources cited include official government statements and social media posts, as well as reporting and interview transcripts from Russian state media outlets, which are, for the purposes of this research, treated as primary sources for analyzing Russian disinformation narratives.

Historical Background

Svalbard has a peculiar international status. Virtue of a 1920 treaty, the archipelago is sovereign Norwegian territory. However, the citizens of signatories of this treaty enjoy the same rights as Norwegian citizens with regard to residence and economic activity on Svalbard. Among the signatories of this treaty was the Soviet Union, which upon its death passed those signatory privileges to the Russian Federation. And indeed, Russia has paid “particular attention to guarding its interests in the area,” in the words of Lt. Col. Michael Zimmerman.¹ In his paper on the Arctic, Zimmerman argues that Svalbard may become the new “epicenter” of Russia-NATO competition in the north, due to its ambiguous international status and potential to create a rift between NATO countries.² Indeed, Russia is the only

signatory of the 1920 treaty, other than Norway, which has taken advantage of its benefits. The Soviet Union established Arktikugol', a state-owned coal mining company, in 1931, and has continued to operate it ever since. In 1979, about 2,000 Russians lived in the Svalbard settlement of Barentsburg, most of them employed by Arktikugol'. The Soviets, and now Russians, have not been shy about trying to expand those benefits. In 1944, Moscow pushed for joint rule over the islands with Norway, and in 1975 the Soviets established a military colony near the Russian settlement of Barentsburg on Svalbard.³ Russia has also extensively engaged in flag-planting activities in the Arctic more broadly. In 2007, for example, a Russian politician descended in a submarine to the bottom of the Lomonosov Ridge north of Greenland and planted a canister containing a Russian flag. For Victory Day celebrations in 2023, Arktikugol' displayed several flags of the breakaway “Donetsk People's Republic,” the infamous Russian-controlled insurrectionist movement in eastern Ukraine.⁴

It is also worth looking specifically at Arktikugol'. While it has fallen far since the collapse of the Soviet Union, it remains active and has recently signaled its intention to revive its old glory. Its website is modern, active, and regularly posts news releases. Among these are mundane, innocent stories about cultural events in Barentsburg, the opening of gyms, swimming pools, and religious holidays. Earlier in 2024, there was also a story about an “Immortal Regiment” of the “Great Patriotic War,” an annual event in which Russians carry

¹ Michael Zimmerman, “High North and High Stakes: The Svalbard Archipelago Could Be the Epicenter of Rising Tension in the Arctic,” *PRISM* 7, no. 4 (2018): 10. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26542710>.

² *Ibid*, 110 and 114.

³ Marian K. Leighton, *The Soviet Threat to NATO's Northern Flank* (New York: National Strategy Information Center, 1979), 15-16.

⁴ Alexandr' Golts, “The Arctic: A Clash of Interests or Clash of Ambitions,” in *Russia in the Arctic*, ed. Stephen J. Blank (Strategic Studies Institute, July 2011), 43. <https://media.defense.gov/2023/May/04/2003215908/-1/-1/0/2146.PDF>; Miranda Byrant, “Barentsburg: the Norwegian town feeling the chill of the Ukraine War,” *The Guardian*, October 10, 2023. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/oct/10/barentsburg-the-norwegian-town-feeling-the-chill-of-the-ukraine-war>.

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images of their ancestors who fell during World War II, and Arktikugol's participation in the 2024 Eastern Economic Forum.⁵ Arktikugol's General Director Dmitry Negrutsa even participated in an interview with Russian propaganda outlet *The Arctic Century*. During this interview Negrutsa highlighted Russia's Arctic cooperation with BRICS and other "friendly" (to Russia) countries and Arktikugol's commitment to providing a "decent level and quality of life" for Russians on Svalbard. Of particular note, however, is Negrutsa's comment about Arktikugol's research program, which contains as part of its framework the study of the Russian presence in Svalbard "as a unique discipline."⁶

This historical background and Russia's activities on Svalbard are significant. Russia remains committed, as it has for nearly a century, to maintaining a presence in the region. In recent years, Russia has particularly exploited Svalbard's potential as an information operation. Lt. Col. Zimmerman astutely points out that the presence of Russians on Svalbard, representing about 10-20% of the population, creates an opportunity for Russia to try to extend its privileges over the archipelago in the name of defending ethnic Russians.⁷ This fact, among others, explains why Svalbard should remain on the West's radar.

Svalbard's Significance

Before delving deeper into the question of Russian activities in Svalbard, it is worth stepping back to consider why these remote islands are significant at all. Obvious answers include rich oil deposits in the waters surrounding Svalbard and its suitability for fishing. But fish are hardly a key strategic resource and Arctic oil remains difficult to obtain under year-long ice. Rather, one should look at the islands' geographic position to understand their importance. Fears have abounded since Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 that Moscow will launch an apocalyptic World War III with NATO by storming Poland and the Baltic States, slicing through the Suwalki Gap, or striking Ukraine with nuclear weapons. Undoubtedly, Russia would like to dismantle NATO. However, such scenarios as those above represent a type of spectacular suicide for Russia that even Vladimir Putin would not wish to experience. Besides, there are far easier ways to destroy NATO's unity and effectiveness. One possible method: launch an incursion into a remote region, one that would trigger NATO's Article 5. Nations would be obligated to retaliate against Russia but would be reluctant to send their own soldiers to die over a barren place in the Arctic.⁸

⁵ "Basseyn otkryt," ["The swimming pool is open"] Arktikugol', March 20, 2024, <https://www.arcticugol.ru/news/bassejn-otkryt>; "Bessmertnyy polk v Piramidye," ["Immortal regiment in Pyramid"] Arktikugol', May 13, 2024, <https://www.arcticugol.ru/news/bessmertnyj-polk-v-piramide>; "Otkryt trenazhyorny zal 'Trud,'" ["The gym 'Labor' is open"] Arktikugol', June 14, 2024, <https://www.arcticugol.ru/news/otkryt-trenazhernyj-zal-trud>; "V domovoy tserkvi DK v den' pamayti Svyatykh Ottsov vpervye za dolgoye vremya sostoyalas' Bozhestvennaya Liturgiya," ["In the house church of DK on the Day of Memory of Holy Fathers a holy liturgy was held for the first instance in a long time"] Arktikugol', June 17, 2024, <https://www.arcticugol.ru/news/v-domovoj-cerkvi-dk-v-den-pamjati-svjatyh-otcov-vpervye-za-dolgoe-vremja-sostojalas>

[bozhestvennaja-liturgija](#); "Trest 'Arktikugol' uchastvuyet v Vostochnom ekonomicheskom forume," [The trust 'Arktikugol' is participating in the Eastern Economic Forum"] Arktikugol', September 2, 2024, <https://www.arcticugol.ru/news/trest-arktugol-uchastvuet-v-vostochnom-ekonomicheskom-forume>.

⁶ Rina Rumyantseva, "The Arktikugol' Trust: Past, Present, and Future in Svalbard," *The Arctic Century*, December 28, 2023, <https://acentury.online/articles/the-arktugol-trust-past-present-and-future-in-svalbard/>.

⁷ Zimmerman, "High North and High Stakes," 7.

⁸ Anders Puck Nielsen, "NATO-Russia war: Can it really happen?" Youtube Video. January 27, 2024. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZY7GPBSyONU>. See

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An additional element of Svalbard's significance is its proximity to other valuable territories. It is about equal distance (600 miles) from both northern Norway and Murmansk, home of Russia's North Sea Fleet. Of arguably more importance militarily, it is just 220 miles west of Franz Josef Land, where Russia's Nagurskoye Air Base is located. This base was constructed in 2014—shortly after Russia's annexation of Crimea—and is home to a contingent of Russian stealth bombers.⁹ This investment of resources, as well as Russia's own naval doctrine for the year 2022, show that the Arctic is a vital interest for Russia. Of particular interest to the Russians are Svalbard and Franz Josef Land.¹⁰

As already established, Svalbard is home to a significant Russian diaspora and Russian state interests in the form of Arktikugol'. These alone provide enough justification to the Russians for any form of military action. To Russia and its revisionist regime, a single act of "oppression" towards ethnic Russian would be sufficient provocation to necessitate intervention. This gives Svalbard great potential for Russian disinformation campaigns. Russia has already gone forward with a bizarre claim, reminiscent of those hedged against Ukraine, that Norway is facilitating a U.S. biological weapons program in the Arctic.¹¹ While this claim has not been pushed into the mainstream, Russia has clearly sown the seeds for a more aggressive info operation in the future.

here for more speculation on the possibilities of a Russian incursion into remote areas of NATO.

⁹ Nick Paton Walsh, "Satellite images show huge Russian military buildup in the Arctic," *CNN*, April 5, 2021, <https://www.cnn.com/2021/04/05/europe/russia-arctic-nato-military-intl-cmd/index.html>.

¹⁰ Russia Maritime Studies Institute, *Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation*, July 31, 2022, 22, <https://dnnlgwick.blob.core.windows.net/portals/0/NWCDepartments/Russia%20Maritime%20Studies%20Institute/2022073>

The Catch

It is so far clear that the Arctic interests the Russians. Their presence there is persistent and growing. They have laid the groundwork for justifying aggressive action: they could concoct stories of the Norwegian government imposing its own oppressive laws on Svalbard, of Norway trying to expel Russians from the archipelago, of Norway disrespecting Russian cultural celebrations on Victory Day, or any other number of misleading and delusional stories. This could be used to justify a special military operation into Svalbard to protect ethnic Russians. But it is difficult to imagine Russia succeeding in such an endeavor. Russia's naval capabilities are very limited compared to those of the United States (not to mention other NATO allies), and have been dramatically reduced over the past two years by Ukraine sinking ships in the Black Sea. Furthermore, so long as the war in Ukraine rages, Russia has no incentive or capability to open a new conflict in the Arctic. Russia currently presents a limited military threat to the Arctic, and it would not be in their interest to dedicate significant amounts of resources to securing dominance in the region while they are engaged in other theaters.

Polar Leverage

Despite the relative lack of immediate, serious danger to Svalbard and the Arctic from

[1_ENG_RUS_Maritime_Doctrine_FINALtxt.pdf?sv=2017-04-17&sr=b&si=DNNFileManagerPolicy&sig=2zUFSaTUSPcOpQDBk%2FuCtVnb%2FDoy06Cbh0EI5tGpl2Y%3D.](#)

¹¹ Thomas Nilsen, "Isolated Russia invites faraway countries to upcoming Svalbard science center in Pyramiden," *Arctic Today*, October 31, 2023, <https://www.arctictoday.com/isolated-russia-invites-faraway-countries-to-upcoming-svalbard-science-center-in-pyramiden/>.

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Russia, the West should not assume that the correct course of action is to simply preserve the status quo. Russia certainly has interests in the north. If Russia prevails in Ukraine, Moscow may turn its gaze towards the Arctic as it seeks to further assert itself and strike at NATO unity; Russia has already made it clear that it wants to pursue Arctic ambitions at some point. Therefore, rather than maintain the status quo, NATO should seize the opportunity that Russia's preoccupation with Ukraine presents and take the initiative in putting Russia on the back foot in the Arctic; Svalbard presents an opportunity to do so.

As previously established, Svalbard is closest to Franz Josef Land, a Russian possession—not to mainland Norway, Greenland, or Iceland. This would explain at least in part why Russia has an incentive to either keep Svalbard demilitarized or bring it under Moscow's own control. Russia certainly recognizes that a NATO military presence in Svalbard could threaten its own ambitions in the Arctic. This further explains why Russia seeks to emphasize its own people's presence on Svalbard, to stake a claim there without directly trying to occupy it militarily. By primarily focusing on cultural and scientific efforts, Russia can present itself as a legitimate and peaceful actor in the region; any attempt to militarize the islands would be an example of NATO imperialism that seeks to drive Russian citizens from their homes. This keeps NATO paralyzed, unable to act lest it appear as the aggressor.

Despite this, there is considerable incentive for NATO to establish a military presence on Svalbard. The Center for New American Security (CNAS) presents such a scenario in which Russia, bogged down in Ukraine and struggling under the weight of sanctions, tries unsuccessfully to reassert

itself as a great power by taking more aggressive action in the Arctic. In the process Russia squanders valuable and increasingly limited resources to maintain a military presence in the Arctic (and specifically a presence on Svalbard).¹² If NATO were to apply more pressure on Russia by establishing a military presence on Svalbard, Russia may further escalate its activities as it tries to remain relevant in the Arctic, forcing itself into a hopeless spending war with the United States. This spending could take the form of Russia expanding its navy, transferring additional military resources to Franz Josef Land, investing in the expansion of military infrastructure there, or redeploying naval assets from the Baltic Sea to the Arctic.

In the event of a full-scale war between NATO and Russia, Svalbard's unique position would allow the West to dominate the northern waters between Russia and Iceland. During summer months, the constant daylight of the Arctic would enable Svalbard-based NATO aircraft to dominate the skies and easily target Russian ships. In the winter, the frozen waters north of Svalbard would force Russian vessels trying to break into the arctic to pass directly between the archipelago and mainland Norway. If NATO were to also set up a small observation post on Bear Island, almost equidistant from Norway and Svalbard, it could easily police these waters and keep the Russians blocked in the Barents Sea.

Militarizing Svalbard would also reassert NATO's strength and further undermine Russia's already weakened status and influence globally. It could cement NATO's dominance in the north, which has been reinforced by Finland and Sweden's recent entrances into the alliance. The scenario that CNAS presents for an isolated and declining Russia is

¹² Andrea Kendall-Taylor et. al, "Russia in the Arctic," *Center for a New American Security*, September 2022, 6-8, <https://s3.us-east->

[1.amazonaws.com/files.cnas.org/documents/RussiaintheArctic2022_Final.pdf](https://s3.us-east-1.amazonaws.com/files.cnas.org/documents/RussiaintheArctic2022_Final.pdf).

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already playing out to some extent. Russian forces were quickly driven out of northern Ukraine early in the war, then in the fall of 2024 rapidly lost control of Kharkiv and Kherson Oblasts. Figures vary depending on sources, but Russian casualties since the beginning of the full-scale invasion have been enormous, ranging from about 300,000 to more than 600,000.¹³ Ukraine's head of military intelligence claimed in September 2024 that Russia is seeking to end the war before 2026, by which time Russia will be under increasing economic pressure and facing severe manpower shortages.¹⁴ Additional pressure from the north could push the 2026 deadline up.

Svalbard in the Context of the Trump Administration

Since entering office on January 20, 2025, President Donald Trump has expressed significant expansionist tendencies. Regarding the Arctic specifically, Trump has repeatedly discussed a desire for taking control of Greenland, including a blunt statement on March 26 that the United States “[has] to have” Greenland.¹⁵ Trump and many in his administration have additionally adopted a highly Ukraine- and Euro-sceptic stance; Trump himself temporarily froze all American aid to Ukraine on March 3, while Vice President J.D. Vance delivered

a highly critical assessment of European leadership in a speech in Munich, Germany, on February 14.¹⁶ In light of this evolving relationship with the United States, Europe will need to obtain every strategic advantage of its own over Russia. Svalbard can play a role in aiding Europe in its defense without the United States: without possibly American reduced aid in a conflict against Russia, European maritime forces will need additional bases in the north to quickly locate and destroy Russian vessels, particularly submarines.

If Trump changes his stance and adopts a warmer tone on Europe and Ukraine, Svalbard could be a good alternative to Greenland for the president's Arctic focus. Norway and the United States could renegotiate the 1920 Spitsbergen Treaty to ensure greater American economic access to oil within Norway's maritime exclusive economic zones and open the archipelago to American military bases. This would bring direct American economic involvement to Svalbard, creating an incentive for continued U.S. military involvement in the region. Combined with a possible minerals deal between the United States and Ukraine, a Svalbard deal could serve as a motivator for President Trump to remain committed to NATO and Ukraine.

¹³ U.S. Department of Defense, *Opening Remarks by Secretary of Defense Lloyd J. Austin III at the 24th Ukraine Defense Contact Group (As Delivered)*, September 6, 2024, <https://www.defense.gov/News/Speeches/Speech/Article/3896714/>; Foreign, Commonwealth, and Development Office and Nicholas Aucott, *Russia's illegal war continues to be a military disaster: UK statement to the OSCE*, September 18, 2024, <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/russias-illegal-war-continues-to-be-a-military-disaster-uk-statement-to-the-osce>; General'nyy shtab ZSU [General Staff of the Armed Forces of Ukraine]. 2024. “Zahal'ni boyovi vtraty protyvyuka z 24.02.22 po 23.10.24” [“General military losses of the enemy from February 24, 2022 through October 23, 2024”]. October 23, 2024. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/NTiDQvVYcZazd3Zm/>.

¹⁴ Davit Gasparian et. al, “Russian Offensive Campaign Assessment, September 15, 2024,” *Institute for the Study of War*, September 15, 2024, <https://understandingwar.org/backgrounder/russian-offensive-campaign-assessment-september-15-2024>.

¹⁵ Danny Nguyen, “‘We have to have it’: Trump ups the pressure on Greenland,” *Politico*, March 2, 2025, <https://www.politico.com/news/2025/03/26/trump-greenland-vance-visit-00004791>.

¹⁶ Kayla Epstein, “Trump faces pushback in Washington over Ukraine aid freeze,” *BBC*, March 4, 2025, <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cp8l25453130>; Emily Atkinson, “JD Vance attacks Europe over free speech and migration,” *BBC*, February 15, 2025, <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/ceve3wl21x1o>.

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Conclusion

Svalbard is a unique place caught at a unique point in history. Its remoteness and small, sparse population mean that Russia can undertake various covert and information operations without fear of major retaliation. An established national presence on Svalbard gives Putin the oft-cited justification of “protecting” ethnic Russians against foreign oppression/aggression. Its proximity to Franz Josef Land and Russian military assets there means that Russia cannot simply ignore it. Establishing military control of Svalbard would give NATO total gatekeeping powers to the Norwegian Sea, as any Russian ships and aircraft trying to break out into the North Atlantic would have to pass directly between mainland Norway and Svalbard.

One should also not forget the impact climate change will have on the Arctic in the long term. The waters north of Svalbard usually remain covered in ice year-round, but warming has resulted in some shrinkage of the ice coverage, and a recent projection suggested that the Arctic could be ice-free during the summer by as early as 2035.¹⁷ An ice-free Arctic would allow Russian ships and submarines, in the event of a conflict with NATO, to sail north of

Svalbard and thus bypass the northern coast of Norway on their way into the Greenland Sea and North Atlantic. So long as Svalbard remains demilitarized, it cannot blunt any Russian advances deep into the Arctic.

There are many incentives for NATO to reconsider Svalbard’s status. Military bases there in the near term could put Russia on the back foot and apply further pressure at a time when Russia is already struggling in Ukraine. In the long term, Svalbard can serve as a vital NATO asset in the Arctic: a counterweight to Russian bases on Franz Josef Land and a sentry over the northern passages from the Barents Sea into the North Atlantic. There are obviously challenges from a legal standpoint in terms of militarizing Svalbard. It is therefore of vital importance that no single member of NATO, including Norway itself, act unilaterally. NATO should also make it clear that it does not intend to expel Russia from Svalbard. However, in the face of an aggressor that flagrantly violates international law, NATO cannot itself be chained to self-imposed restraints. Svalbard is a crucial asset to both Russia and NATO. The latter should secure it.

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Jacob Spencer is a second-year graduate student at the Institute of World Politics. His key areas of study include cognitive warfare and disinformation, the geopolitics of the post-Soviet sphere, and democratic backsliding and authoritarian creep in the West. He holds a bachelor's degree in history from the University of Arkansas at Monticello and a Teaching English as a Foreign Language certificate from International TEFL Academy.

Photo by Francesco Ungaro: <https://www.pexels.com/photo/view-of-a-fjord-19968770/>

¹⁷ Alexandra Jahn, Marika M. Holland, and Jennifer E. Kay, “Projections of an ice-free Arctic Ocean,” *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment* 5 (March 2024), 170, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43017-023-00515-9.epdf>.

See quote: “Consistently ice-free conditions are expected by mid-century, potentially under all warming scenarios. Predictions for consistently ice-free conditions range from 2023 to 2085, with refined projections of 2035–2067.”

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